

Implementation of digestion and characterization procedures for control standardization on samples of Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*) and plastic polymers from the coastal environment of the Asinara Gulf (Sardinia, Italy)

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the present study was the implementation of a digestion procedure along with Fourier transform infrared microscopy (μ -FTIR) analysis for control standardization on samples of Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*) and different types of plastic polymers isolated in the coastal environment of the Asinara Gulf (Sardinia, Italy). The study has been carried out across two steps, the first of which was necessary to evaluate the exact amount of potassium hydroxide (KOH) at 10 % to degrade the organic matrix of gastro-intestinal tract and muscle of Gilthead Seabream samples as much as possible without causing alterations to the eventual polymers that may be present. Moreover, the possible effects of 10 % KOH at 60 °C for 48 and 72 h and at 40 °C for 48 h were evaluated through the examination of plastic polymers that can be easily ingested by aquatic organisms under the Stereomicroscope and Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). The second step involved the characterization of these plastic polymers by μ -FTIR. The results showed that the use of 1/10 KOH 10 % proved to be the most effective for the digestion of animal tissues, but at the same time (40 °C for 48 h) able to guarantee a lower impact on plastics and greater time savings. The characterization of plastic polymers by μ -FTIR revealed that the samples isolated from the coastal environment of the Asinara Gulf (Sardinia, Italy) were mostly represented by polyethylene, nylon, polyethylene terephthalate, polystyrene, polypropylene and polyurethane. These plastic polymers can be easily ingested by aquatic organisms and humans are exposed to them via their consumption, but so far, the consequences and potential risks have not yet been quantified. The results of the present study represent a preliminary contribution to the control standardization on samples of Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*) and different types of plastic polymers isolated in Sardinian coastal environments.

1. Introduction

The term "plastics" refers to non-biodegradable organic polymers which, due to their extremely advantageous characteristics (versatility, high durability, resistance to water and corrosion, low weight), have been widely used in several sectors. Global plastic production in recent years stands at around 367 million tons (Plastic Europe, 2021). Due to its strength, durability and the difficulty of proper disposal, plastic waste is

invading various ecosystems, in particular the marine environment. The Mediterranean Sea is among the marine environments with the greatest accumulation of marine plastic litter due to its semi-closed structure, the limited flow of surface waters, a densely populated coastline and the intensity of human activities (fishing, navigation, tourism and industry) (Van Sibylle et al., 2015). Plastic polymers, once in the environment, through various physical, chemical and biological alteration processes such as photodegradation or thermal degradation, can change density

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Fig. 1. Sampling location in the Gulf of Asinara, Sardinia, Italy, marked with a yellow circle (GPS coordinates: 40.890585 N, 8.272962 E). The map was modified from Google Maps (<https://mapstyle.withgoogle.com/>; accessed on November 24, 2024).

Table 1
Identification and characterization of plastic polymers collected in the coastal environment of the Asinara Gulf (Sardinia, Italy).

Number	Identification	Characterization (μ -FTIR)
1	Bottle cap	Low-density Polyethylene (LDPE)
2	Food bag	Low-density Polyethylene (LDPE)
3	Fishing line	Nylon
4	Packaging chips	Starch
5	Packaging balls	Low-density Polyethylene (LDPE)
6	Water bottle	Polyethylene terephthalate (PET)
7	Screw cap	Polystyrene (PS)
8	Expanded Packaging material	Polystyrene (PS)
9	Commercial product containers	Polypropylene (PP)
10	Foam rubber for padding	Polyurethane

and can be reduced to smaller and smaller fragments, giving rise to microplastics (MP). Attention to these contaminants has grown enormously in recent years, also in consideration of the probable environmental and health repercussions to which they have been associated. MP

are a huge problem for aquatic ecosystems (Eriksen et al., 2013; Castañeda et al., 2014; Ivar do Sul & Costa, 2014). A recent survey carried out in the Mediterranean area found that the most frequent polymers were low- and high-density polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polystyrene (PS), widely used in the plastics industry (de Haan William et al., 2019). In particular, an average concentration of 0.116 fragments/m² of surface area was found, up to a maximum of over 0.36 fragments/m² off the Island of Elba (Collignon et al., 2012). Similar results have been found in studies conducted in Corsica and Sardinia (Corbau et al., 2020). As far as the Sea of Sardinia, the concentrations of MP would be variable, with generally medium-high densities. It is assumed that the variability found may be due to turbulence phenomena and the wind that insists on Sardinia (Corbau et al., 2020). Given the wide diffusion in the marine environment, MP can be easily ingested by aquatic organisms. Their presence has been demonstrated in zooplankton, bivalve molluscs, crustaceans and fish (Walkinshaw et al., 2020; Cau et al., 2019). In fish, the presence of MP has been detected in different organs: the gastrointestinal tract was consistently the most contaminated, followed by gills, while the lowest density was found in

Fig. 2. Effects of the trial A (60 °C for 48 h) on sample n.1 (plastic bottle cap).

Fig. 3. Presence of vesicles on sample n.1 (plastic bottle cap) after the trial A (60 °C for 48 h).

Fig. 4. Effects of the trial A (60 °C for 48 h) on sample n.2 (food bag).

Fig. 5. Effects of the trial A (60 °C for 48 h) on sample n.3 (fishing line).

muscles and brain (Atamanalp et al., 2021). Given the wide diffusion in the environment, MP can be ingested for direct consumption or enter the food chain and then accumulate in animals at the top of the food chain, including humans (Hollman et al., 2013). The possible risk to human health caused by the presence of MP is still being studied: chronic exposure is of great concern because of the cumulative effect that could occur. (Martellone et al., 2021). A starting point for an effective assessment of the risk for the consumer requires knowledge of the level of contamination and an accurate identification and quantification of MP in seafood, one of the main sources of animal protein in human nutrition. There are still no standardized methods for the research and characterization of plastic polymers and is necessary to develop accurate digestion and characterization techniques for control standardization on fish samples and plastic polymers. The objectives of the present

investigation were: a) to evaluate the effects of reagents and digestion procedures on samples of Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*) and plastic polymers, from the coastal environment of the Asinara Gulf (Sardinia, Italy); b) to characterize the same plastic polymers through the use of Fourier transform infrared microscopy (μ -FTIR). These plastic polymers are widely diffused and can be easily ingested by aquatic organisms. The results of the present study will contribute to their identification and characterization in future studies carried out in Sardinian coastal environments.

Fig. 6. Presence of newly formed elements on sample n.3 (fishing line) after the trial A (60 °C for 48 h).

Fig. 7. Effects of the trial A (60 °C for 48 h) on sample n.4 (packaging chips).

Fig. 8. Effects of the trial A (60 °C for 48 h) on sample n.5 (packaging balls).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Implementation of the digestion procedure on samples of Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*)

A total of fifteen wild Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*) samples were randomly collected from the local commercial catch of the trawl fishery in the Asinara Gulf (Sardinia, Italy) and used to define the ratio (reagent/matrix) capable of degrading organic matter (Fig. 1). Test samples for each matrix (gastro-intestinal tract, GI and muscle, M) were digested using KOH 10 % in different proportions. The tested reagent/matrix were: 1:3, 1:5 and 1:10, i.e. using respectively 3, 5 and 10 ml of KOH 10 % for each gram of product. Five repetitions were carried out for

each tested proportion. After digestion, the samples were filtered through polycarbonate filters with porosity of 10 µm and 47–50 mm in diameter (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) by a vacuum pump (Thermo Savant VLP200 Valu Pump, Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA). In order to evaluate the degradation of organic matter and the possible effects of KOH 10 %, the filters were examined by using a Zeiss Stemi 200-C optical stereo-microscope, a Leica DMS1000 digital stereo-microscope and a Leo EVO 50 VP scanning electron microscope (SEM).

2.2. Implementation of the digestion procedure on samples of plastic polymers

The aim was to verify the suitability of the digestive protocol adopted for the release of MP from the biota by studying any physical changes in the polymers eventually present. In order to investigate the effect of the of KOH 10 % solution, ten different types of plastic polymers that can be easily ingested by aquatic organisms were collected in the coastal environment of the Asinara Gulf (Sardinia, Italy) as can be seen in Table 1. MP (> 500 µm) were obtained from each polymer and samples were prepared with artificially contaminated digestion solution (KOH 10 %). Three different experiments (A→C) were set up using 10 % KOH solutions in different time-temperature combinations, namely: trial A (60 °C for 48 h), trial B (60 °C for 72 h), trial C (40 °C for 48 h). After digestion, the samples were filtered through polycarbonate filters with porosity of 10 µm and 47–50 mm in diameter (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) by a vacuum pump (Thermo Savant VLP200 Valu Pump, Thermo Fischer Scientific, USA). In order to evaluate the degradation of plastic polymers, the filters were examined by using a Zeiss Stemi 200-C optical stereo-microscope, a Leica DMS1000 digital stereo-microscope and a Leo EVO 50 VP scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Fig. 9. Presence of newly formed elements on sample n.5 (packaging balls) after the trial A (60 °C for 48 h).

Fig. 10. Effects of the trial B (60 °C for 72 h) on sample n.1 (plastic bottle cap).

Fig. 11. Effects of the trial B (60 °C for 72 h) on sample n.4 (packaging chips).

2.3. Characterization of plastic polymers by Fourier transform infrared microscopy (μ -FTIR)

The same plastic polymers used to verify the suitability of the digestive protocol (Table 1) were characterized by Fourier transform infrared microscopy (μ -FTIR). For each plastic polymer, particles > 500 μ m in size were prepared. Subsequently, the individual particles were identified by means of the Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR)-FTIR. Briefly, fragments in the micrometric size visible under a light stereomicroscope were manually removed from filters and washed in a 2 mL vial with DI water for removing organic residues from digestion. The fragments were further fished from the solution and deposited onto the diamond culet of a diamond compression cell for flattening the sample. Transmission measurements were performed achieving a lateral resolution up to few microns, exploiting the brightness of Infrared

Synchrotron Radiation. Collected spectra were compared with reference spectra in order to exclude laboratory contamination and identify if they belonged to the more common classes of founded plastic polymers.

3. Results

3.1. Implementation of the digestion procedure on samples of Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*)

The preparation of test samples with different proportions of reagent (KOH 10 %) with respect to the matrix to be digested (M or GI) was carried out considering three matrix/reagent proportions: 1:3, 1:5 and 1:10. Several studies have shown that the use of high concentrations of reagents and/or high incubation temperatures cause involve high degradation rates (Brown et al., 2001). As reported in previous studies

Fig. 12. Effects of the trial B (60 °C for 72 h) on sample n.5 (packaging balls).

Fig. 13. Characterization of sample n.1 (bottle cap/LDPE) by μ -FTIR.

(Thiele et al., 2019), our results showed that only the use of the 1:10 ratio, guaranteed an optimal digestion of both M and GI samples. At the same time, the filters did not show alterations when observed under the stereomicroscope.

3.2. Implementation of the digestion procedure on samples of plastic polymers

3.2.1. Trial A (60 °C for 48 h)

The most important alterations have been showed on samples n.1–5. The sample n.1 (plastic bottle cap) showed softer shapes and coarse filamentous parts (Fig. 2). The most evident alteration was on the surface showing vesicles of 10–15 μ m in diameter (Fig. 3). The structure of the sample n.2 (food bag) was highly modified with the presence of rounded shape elements on the surface and with eruptions of microbubbles (Fig. 4). Also in sample n.3 (fishing line) the eruption of microbubbles has been pointed out together with the presence of corrosion (Fig. 5). At higher magnifications (2500–3000 MAG), a large number of elements

likely to be newly formed has been highlighted (Fig. 6). The presence of newly formed elements has been showed also on sample n.4 (packaging chips). Only a small part of the original structure has been preserved (Fig. 7). The general appearance of sample n.5 (packaging balls) is largely affected by the presence of yellowish newly formed elements (Fig. 8). The eruption of microbubbles on the surface of these neoformations was observed (Fig. 9).

3.2.2. Trial B (60 °C for 72 h)

The most important alterations have been showed on samples n.1, n.3, n.4 and n.5. In sample n.1 (plastic bottle cap) the eruption of microbubbles on the surface was observed (Fig. 10). The Sample n.3 (fishing line) presented localized eruptions such as microbubbles. The original structure of sample n.4 (packaging chips) and sample n.5 (packaging balls) was not recognizable at all (Fig. 11 and 12 respectively). In particular, sample n.5 presented a strong yellowish deposit characterized by newly formed elements with presence of K, Si, Ca, Mg, Al.

Fig. 14. Characterization of sample n.2 (food bag/LDPE) by μ -FTIR.

Fig. 15. Characterization of sample n.3 (fishing line/Nylon) by μ -FTIR.

3.2.3. Trial C (40 °C for 48 h)

No substantial changes have been observed on the treated polymers which retain their original characteristics.

3.3. Characterization of plastic polymers by Fourier transform infrared microscopy (μ -FTIR)

The characterization of plastic polymers by μ -FTIR are reported below and are summarized in Table 1. The sample n.1 (plastic bottle cap) consisted of low-density polyethylene (LDPE). The results highlighted that this product was made of 70 % recycled polyethylene from packaging film waste. In Fig. 13, the spectrum of sample n.1 (in red) is observed in overlay with the spectrum of LPDE 70 (in green) which showed the best match ratio (96.32 %). Polyethylene is the dominant form of polymers in the Mediterranean Sea; in particular, LDPE has high flexibility and due to its easy processing, it is used as a constituent in supermarket plastic bags and also used as a wrap for different food

products (Bayo et al., 2018). Sample n.2 (food bag) consisted of LDPE (Fig. 14). The spectrum of sample n.2 (in red) and the spectrum of LDPE (in green) are observed in overlay, which, among all the libraries, showed the best match ratio (82 %). It should be noted that the peak between 2000 and 2500 is related to CO₂. The study on sample n.3 (fishing line) was performed in transmission mode by exploiting the transparency of this material which is therefore crossed by the IR beam (Fig. 15). The results revealed that the sample was composed mainly by nylon fiber (70 %) and for the remaining 30 % by acrylic resin thickener. The spectrum of the nylon fiber (in green) can be observed in overlay with the sample spectrum (in blue). The combination of the two components showed the match ratio of 52.89 %. The study on sample n.4 (packaging chips) showed that it consisted of starch (Fig. 16). Although at first glance is commonly believed that they are made from plastic materials, the results showed that packaging chips are compostable natural material obtained from starch and used to make foamy packaging. Starch is biodegradable, so starch foam is being used as an

Fig. 16. Characterization of sample n.4 (packaging chips/Starch) by μ -FTIR.

Fig. 17. Characterization of sample n.5 (packaging balls/LDPE) by μ -FTIR.

environmentally friendly alternative to expanded polystyrene packaging. Sample n.5 (packaging balls) constitute the basic material for the packing of many different processed products. They were made up of LDPE (Fig. 17). The spectrum of sample n.5 (in red) is observed in overlay with the spectrum of LDPE (in purple) which showed the best match ratio (97.27 %) match. Sample n.6 (water bottle) was made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET). Fig. 18 showed the overlay of the spectrums: sample n.6 (in red) and PET (in purple) with a match ratio of 84 %. As reported in Fig. 19, sample n.7 (screw cap) consisted of polystyrene (PS). A match ratio of 78 % was pointed out between the overlay

of the two spectrums: sample n.7 (in red) and PS (in light blue). Also the sample n.8 (expanded packaging material) consisted of PS, a material largely used for fragile packaging. The spectrum of sample n.8 (in red) showed a match ratio of 73 % (Fig. 20) with the spectrum of PS (in purple). Sample n.9 (commercial product containers) consisted of polypropylene (PP). In general, the environmental dispersion of these samples increases over the Easter period, as these disposable containers are often associated with Easter eggs. As reported in Fig. 21, the spectrum of sample n.9 (in red) is observed in overlay with the spectrum of PP (in purple) which showed the best match ratio (74 %). Sample n.10

Fig. 18. Characterization of sample n.6 (water bottle/PET) by μ -FTIR.

Fig. 19. Characterization of sample n.7 (screw cap/PS) by μ -FTIR.

(foam rubber for padding) consisted of polyurethane. The spectrum of sample n.10 (in red) showed a match ratio of 56 % (Fig. 22) with the spectrum of polyurethane (in purple). LDPE, PP and PS contributed significantly to the overall polymer composition. Being widely used in the disposable packaging industry and having lower densities than seawater, it is not surprising that these polymers consistently account for the majority of the plastic particles floating in surface waters worldwide (Reisser et al., 2013; Hidalgo-Ruz et al., 2012; Frias et al., 2014). These results are in line with data on the distribution of plastic polymers in seafood, suggesting that packaging materials and textile products could be considered as an important source of exposure for aquatic organisms in the western and eastern Mediterranean (Suaria et al., 2016; Cau et al., 2019; de Haan William et al., 2019; Adamopoulou et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2021).

4. Conclusions

The results of the present study on the impact of digestion (activity of KOH 10 %) and attack (times/temperatures) on the plastic polymers showed that the combinations of trial A (60 °C for 48 h) and trial B (60 °C for 72 h) had a strong degradation effect. After SEM observation, diffuse phenomena of partial fusion of plastics with the appearance of eruptions as microbubbles have been pointed out. These two combinations present the high risk that small plastic elements may become barely visible after the attack of biological tissues. On the contrary, the digestion procedure at 40 °C and for a time of 48 h (trial C) proved to be the most effective, sufficient for the digestion of animal tissues, but able to guarantee a lower impact on plastics and greater time savings. The μ -FTIR characterization of plastic samples collected in the coastal environments of the Asinara Gulf (Sardinia, Italy) revealed that they were mostly represented by 6 different polymers: polyethylene (PE), nylon, polyethylene terephthalate, polystyrene (PS), polypropylene (PP) and

Fig. 20. Characterization of sample n.8 (expanded packaging material/PS) by μ -FTIR.

Fig. 21. Characterization of sample n.9 (commercial product container/PP) by μ -FTIR.

polyurethane. These plastic polymers can be easily ingested by aquatic organisms and humans are exposed to them via their consumption, but so far, the consequences and potential risks have not yet been quantified. The results of the present study represent a preliminary contribution to the control standardization on samples of Gilthead Seabream (*Sparus aurata*) and different types of plastic polymers and will contribute to their identification and characterization in future studies carried out in Sardinian coastal environments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Rita Melillo: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Roberto Lonis:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Giuseppa Lorenzoni:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gabriella Piras:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nicola Cogoni:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Simona Cau:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis,

Data curation. **Sara Salza:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Riccardo Bazzardi:** Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Monica Molotzu:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Giuseppe Esposito:** Validation, Supervision, Software, Data curation. **Bruna Vodret:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Domenico Meloni:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Sebastiano Virgilio:** Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Fig. 22. Characterization of sample n.10 (foam rubber for padding/Polyurethane) by μ -FTIR.

Ethical Statement: studies in humans and animals

The authors declare that the work do not involves the use of human or animal subjects

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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